

Comparative Evaluation of Reference Data Sources for Land-Cover Classification: Insta360 Panoramas vs. Orthophotos and Satellite Imagery

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Abstract: Reliable ground-truth reference data are critical for training and validating land-cover classification, and the choice of data source directly affects the informativeness, reliability, and operational applicability of the results. This manuscript proposes a methodology for the comparative evaluation of candidate ground-truth reference data sources using the same sample of 50 locations. The analysis compares terrestrial panoramas captured with an Insta360 camera, the national digital orthophoto map (DOF), and PlanetScope and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery, with qualitative consideration of drone orthophotos and very-high-resolution satellite basemaps (VHR Google Earth) where available. The reference land-cover label at the main-class level is defined by expert consensus and used as the operational reference standard for source comparison. The evaluation includes the number of fine, structurally defined classes that can be reliably identified from each source, the level of inter-expert agreement, and standard agreement metrics at the main-class level. The literature indicates a lack of systematic comparisons of terrestrial 360° panoramas with traditional top-down sources as candidates for generating ground-truth reference data, which this study addresses. At Level 2, inter-expert agreement (Cohen's kappa) was 0.85 (DOF), 0.83 (Insta360), 0.77 (PlanetScope), and 0.74 (Sentinel-2), while OA against Ref_N2 was highest for DOF (0.86), followed by PlanetScope (0.68) and Sentinel-2 (0.52). The results show that Insta360 panoramas enable recognition of a larger number of fine land-cover classes with pronounced vertical structure. For top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2), quantitative comparison shows different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level. The combination of high detail and terrestrial perspective, together with low additional time requirements for processing already available imagery, indicates that Insta360 panoramas can be a practical compromise for reference data generation in areas with complex land cover.

Keywords: land cover classification; ground-truth; comparative evaluation; orthophoto and satellite imagery; Insta360 panoramas.

1 Introduction

The quality of land-cover classification does not depend only on the algorithm, it is mostly determined by the choice of ground-truth reference data for training and validation, with different sources involving different trade-offs between informativeness, reliability, and operational feasibility (Congalton and Green 2009). This manuscript

compares terrestrial Insta360 panoramas with the main top-down sources available at all selected locations: DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2.

There are methodological studies on georeferenced 360° (panospheric) imagery and reproducible annotation (Godfree and Knerr 2025, Hristova et al. 2025). However, these studies focus on developing tools and procedures for working with 360° imagery, rather than on a systematic comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against top-down sources. A review of the available literature indicates that such a systematic comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against traditional ground-truth sources in the context of land-cover classification on the same location sample is still lacking.

Most existing studies using street view imagery (SVI) rely on data collected through existing platforms or dedicated acquisition campaigns (Li et al. 2022, Zhou et al. 2025), whereas this manuscript uses targeted, self-acquired Insta360 imagery.

Terrestrial sampling (field survey), i.e., direct site visits and manual class recording, is the reference approach for independent ground truth, but it is not included in this study due to cost, time, and logistical constraints (Congalton and Green 2009, Ali et al. 2022).

In this manuscript, Insta360 panoramas are considered a terrestrially informative and operationally feasible source for generating reference data without additional fieldwork. Independent annotations by Experts A and B are used to assess inter-expert consistency, while the main-class reference label is defined by consensus and used as the operational standard for source comparison. The aim of the manuscript is to examine how Insta360 panoramas compare with DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 in terms of informativeness, reliability, and operational feasibility for land-cover classification.

The hypotheses are as follows:

H1: Insta360 panoramas enable recognition of a significantly larger number of fine land-cover classes (Level 1) than DOF and satellite imagery, especially for covers with pronounced vertical structure (permanent crops, shrubland, forest).

H2: The reliability and agreement of annotations depend on both source and cover type: Insta360 provides greater informativeness for fine structural differences, while top-down sources show different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level.

2 Materials and methods

This section presents the study area, data and overall methodological approach.

2.1 Study area and data

2.1.1 Study area and location selection

The study area comprises multiple locations in Croatia recorded with an Insta360 camera during several multi-day campaigns along road corridors and at selected off-road points. A total of 50 locations were selected for comparative source evaluation at the same sites, with the sample designed for methodological source comparison rather than for estimating national land-cover class prevalence. The sample size was chosen to ensure stable evaluation of Level 2 metrics, following good-practice recommendations for sampling and accuracy assessment (Olofsson et al. 2014). Stratification across Level 2 land-cover classes was as follows: permanent crops (5), shrubland (8), bare soil/rock (5), forest (15), grassland (7), urban (5), and arable land (5). Locations were selected in an office-based workflow from an existing database of geotagged Insta360 panoramas and available orthophoto/satellite sources, using criteria of reliable GNSS positioning, availability of all main sources, and sufficient scene interpretability. A minimum spatial distance between locations was additionally enforced to avoid selecting very close, mutually similar scenes.

2.1.2 Data

The main sources available at all 50 locations are:

- Insta panoramas: GNSS-geotagged 360° × 180° panoramas forming an archive of existing imagery used for location selection and interpretation.
- DOF: the official digital orthophoto map of the Republic of Croatia, with 0.5 m spatial resolution and systematic nationwide coverage (SGA 2024).
- PlanetScope: high-resolution satellite imagery with 3 m spatial resolution and high temporal availability.
- Sentinel-2: multispectral imagery with 10 m spatial resolution for the bands used, freely available and standardized.

Secondary sources include drone orthophotos (5–10 cm), available for a subset of locations, and very-high-resolution imagery from web mapping services (e.g., Google Earth), which are widely available. In this manuscript, both are used exclusively as qualitative supplementary visual support and are not included in the main quantitative comparison. Here, “qualitative” denotes expert, descriptive insight into source interpretability without formal statistical evaluation across the full sample.

2.2 Methods

This study applies a structured expert visual-interpretation workflow for source comparison rather than an automated classification pipeline. No automated classifier was trained in this study. The term “limited top-down view” refers to a nadir or slightly off-nadir perspective in which top-down sources capture the horizontal projection of land cover,

without detailed insight into vertical structure (height and structure among elements).

2.2.1 Expert annotation and reference standard

Two independent experts (Expert A and Expert B) annotate land-cover class by location and by data source. Annotation is performed using the same two-level classification scheme (7 main classes and 16 fine classes) and a shared protocol. The protocol defines when to assign a fine class (Level 1) and when to remain at the main-class level (Level 2). Independent annotations (A and B) are collected before any reconciliation. Annotations are recorded in a standardized tabular template by location, source, and expert.

In the final dataset, Level 1 (fine classes) is recorded for a given source only when independent annotations by Experts A and B match, in all other cases, only Level 2 is retained. Level 2 (seven main classes) is used as the primary level for quantitative comparisons because it is consistently applicable across all sources in the full sample.

After independent annotation, Ref_N2 is defined for each location as a consensus (A+B) Level 2 class based primarily on terrestrial information from Insta360 panoramas. This Ref_N2 is used as the operational ground-truth reference standard in all quantitative source comparisons.

This choice reflects the fact that the terrestrial perspective of Insta360 panoramas provides the most direct view of the vertical land-cover structure relevant to the applied classification scheme. Top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) often do not capture this information to the same extent. Ref_N2 therefore does not represent an “absolute truth,” but rather a standardized expert reference designed to maximize terrestrial informativeness. Its reliability is further assessed through inter-expert agreement (Cohen’s κ).

2.2.2 Classification scheme

A hierarchical two-level classification scheme was used: Level 2 (main categories) and Level 1 (fine classes). Level 2 comprises seven main classes: permanent crops, shrubland, bare soil/rock, forest, grassland, urban, and arable land. Level 1 subdivides these categories into a total of 16 fine classes, selected to be feasible and reproducible in visual interpretation on a sample of 50 locations and applicable across all analyzed sources.

Fine classes were defined structurally and functionally, independently of data source. They include core subtypes within the main classes (e.g., permanent crops by age and presence of stones, shrubland by the proportion of stone/vegetation, forest by composition, urban surfaces by degree of built-up structure, and arable land by cultivation status and vegetation stage). In the 50-location sample, Level 1 is used primarily descriptively, while quantitative source comparison is performed at Level 2.

2.2.3 Evaluation metrics

To ensure comparability of annotations across sources, a standardized geometry was applied. The starting point was the GNSS coordinate of the Insta360 panorama (on the road), from which a 50 m offset was applied in the direction

of geodetic north, the resulting point was used as the center of the buffer zone. A circular zone with a 10 m radius ($\approx 314 \text{ m}^2$) was defined around this center. This zone is comparable to the pixel size of satellite sources (e.g., $10 \times 10 \text{ m}$ for Sentinel-2, $3 \times 3 \text{ m}$ for PlanetScope), reduces the influence of GNSS error, and enables representative annotation of surrounding land cover.

Insta360 panoramas were annotated in QGIS (Panorama Viewer plugin) with the buffer zone displayed. Sentinel-2 was also analyzed in QGIS, while DOF, PlanetScope, and, where available, drone orthophotos and VHR/Google Earth imagery were interpreted on a WebGIS platform. The standardized geometry ensures that all sources are recorded over the same spatial area, enabling direct comparison.

The descriptive metric “number of recognizable classes” (Level 1) measures the informativeness of a source in distinguishing fine, structurally defined classes. In practical implementation, it is calculated as the number of fine classes (Level 1) that are reliably identified for a given source within the analyzed sample of locations. A higher number of recognizable fine classes indicates greater source informativeness.

2.2.4 Statistical analysis

The consistency of expert annotations for each data source is assessed using Cohen’s unweighted kappa (κ) at Level 2, by comparing independent annotations from Experts A and B before any reconciliation.

For quantitative comparison of top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) at Level 2, a confusion matrix is computed between Pred_N2 and Ref_N2. Here, Pred_N2 denotes the consensus Level 2 class assigned to each source at each location (A+B for that source). Ref_N2 denotes the consensus reference Level 2 class per location, identical across all sources at that location.

From the confusion matrix, standard accuracy metrics are calculated: overall accuracy (OA), producer’s accuracy (PA), user’s accuracy (UA), and F1-score (Foody 2002, Olofsson et al. 2014).

Because Ref_N2 is an operational consensus standard (see 2.2.1), the resulting metrics are interpreted as measures of agreement between top-down sources and that standard. Due to partial circularity, the same metrics are not computed for Insta360, for this source, inter-expert consistency and the number of recognizable fine classes (Level 1) are reported instead.

3 Results

3.1 Number of classes and metrics

For the 50-location sample, Level 2 statistical metrics were computed for top-down sources (DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) relative to Ref_N2. For Insta360, inter-expert consistency (Cohen’s κ) and the number of recognizable fine classes (Level 1) are reported.

At the fine-class level (Level 1), 14 of the 16 fine classes defined in the applied classification scheme were represented in the selected 50-location sample. For

Insta360, all 14 represented fine classes were recognized in the sample. In contrast, DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 showed limited ability to reliably distinguish fine classes.

Inter-expert consistency at Level 2 (Cohen’s κ) is 0.85 for DOF, 0.83 for Insta360, 0.77 for PlanetScope, and 0.74 for Sentinel-2. Differences among sources primarily arise from class pairs that most frequently generate disagreement: shrubland–forest, permanent crops–arable land, and grassland–arable land, especially in satellite sources. The obtained Cohen’s κ values indicate good to very high inter-expert consistency at Level 2, with expected differences among sources.

Table 1 summarizes overall accuracy (OA) and PA/UA/F1 ranges (min-max) across Level 2 classes for DOF, PlanetScope, and Sentinel-2 relative to operational reference standard Ref_N2.

Table 1. Accuracy metrics for top-down sources relative to Ref_N2 at Level 2.

Source	OA	PA (min-max)	UA (min-max)	F1 (min-max)
DOF	0.86	0.60 – 1.00	0.56 – 1.00	0.59 – 1.00
PlanetScope	0.68	0.00 – 1.00	0.40 – 1.00	0.50 – 0.91
Sentinel-2	0.52	0.00 – 0.93	0.21 – 1.00	0.32 – 0.80

Because the number of locations per class is small (5-15), class-level minimum and maximum values should be interpreted with caution, as one or a few misclassifications may disproportionately affect the range, especially the minimum. Nevertheless, comparison of OA and metric ranges across sources clearly shows the expected order of agreement with the reference standard (DOF > PlanetScope > Sentinel-2), consistent with source spatial resolution and viewing perspective.

Differences among sources are most evident in classes located at class boundaries or in heterogeneous areas within the sample geometry, and in classes whose visual signal changes seasonally or operationally. In DOF, lower values are mainly driven by shrubland and bare soil/rock, while forest, grassland, urban, and arable land show consistently high values. For PlanetScope, minima are driven by permanent crops (absence of correct class assignments) and arable land, whereas forest and urban are among the more reliable classes. For Sentinel-2, the lowest values are linked to permanent crops, shrubland, and arable land, while forest and urban surfaces retain relatively better values than the remaining classes.

This pattern confirms that, at Level 2, classes with clearer spatial structure and higher homogeneity are more reliably distinguished, whereas coarser satellite sources are more frequently affected by land-cover mixing within a small sample geometry.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation and validation of results

The observed patterns in the number of recognizable classes (Level 1) and Level 2 accuracy metrics primarily arise from differences in source perspective (terrestrial vs. top-down) and spatial resolution. In this context, top-down sources provide a clearer overview of the spatial arrangement of land cover and more stable interpretation under homogeneous conditions.

Scalability and practical applicability further influence result interpretation. Sources that are widely available or free (e.g., DOF, Sentinel-2, and existing Insta360 panoramas) enable application of the methodology to a larger number of locations with low additional time cost per location. Here, additional time cost per location refers to the time needed for source data access, visual interpretation, and annotation entry using already available data, without new data acquisition or field visits.

4.2 Source characteristics and applicability

Insta panoramas provide a $360^\circ \times 180^\circ$ terrestrial perspective that enables recognition of fine classes associated with vertical structure (forest, permanent crops), which are often not reliably distinguishable from a top-down view. Limitations arise from the fact that, in practice, image acquisition is concentrated along road corridors and temporal coverage depends on acquisition campaigns, which may constrain representativeness for some land-cover types.

DOF provides systematic full-area coverage at high spatial resolution and is particularly suitable for the interpretation of larger areas. PlanetScope (3 m) and Sentinel-2 (10 m) represent satellite sources with different trade-offs between spatial and temporal resolution. PlanetScope is more informative for Level 2 analyses, whereas Sentinel-2 is operationally highly available and standardized but limited in recognizing fine classes due to spatial resolution and nadir perspective.

Drone orthophotos and VHR basemaps (e.g., Google Earth) provide very detailed insight into land-cover structure, but in this manuscript they are used only as qualitative support because of limited availability and operational constraints.

Overall, Insta360 and DOF cover most reference-data needs at the selected locations, while satellite and VHR sources have specialized roles depending on scale and availability.

A slightly lower Cohen's kappa value for Insta360 than for DOF does not imply an inferior source, rather, it reflects the greater detail in Insta imagery: a larger amount of visible local elements can increase the likelihood of expert disagreement in edge cases and allow more legitimate annotation interpretations. In contrast, DOF at the main-class level often provides a more stable signal for inter-expert agreement.

In this study, source acquisition dates were not fully synchronous because the most recent available datasets differed by source (DOF 2022, PlanetScope 2024, Insta360 2025). Sentinel-2 imagery was available for the same period as Insta360 acquisition, while for PlanetScope both

winter and summer scenes were available and considered during interpretation. To reduce temporal bias, locations were selected where no evident major land-cover change was observed across the available dates. This supports basic comparability for structurally defined Level 2 classes, however, subtle inter-annual and seasonal variability cannot be fully excluded, particularly for management-sensitive classes such as permanent crops and arable land. These effects are therefore treated as a limitation when interpreting agreement among sources.

Because Ref_N2 was defined primarily from Insta360-based consensus, agreement metrics for top-down sources may be biased downward in classes where vertical structure is weakly represented in nadir imagery. This trade-off was accepted because the study objective was to maximize structurally informative reference labeling under operational constraints.

Positioned against related studies, this manuscript addresses a different research question. Godfree and Knerr (2025) focus on reproducible ecological data collection and annotation from 360° imagery, while Hristova et al. (2025) focus on videogrammetry-based 3D reconstruction for forest inventory. In contrast, this study provides a comparative evaluation of multiple reference-data sources (Insta360, DOF, PlanetScope, Sentinel-2) on the same location sample for land-cover classification. Its scientific contribution is an operational comparative framework that combines Level 1 informativeness (number of recognizable fine classes) with Level 2 agreement-based evaluation (Cohen's kappa, OA, PA, UA, F1) under explicitly stated reference-standard assumptions.

4.3 Insta360 vs. field survey for land-cover classification

For visual land-cover classification at the level of structural attributes, georeferenced Insta360 panoramas can serve as an operational proxy for terrestrial insight. They enable scene inspection from a ground-level perspective and reproducible expert annotation without requiring repeated field visits. Inter-expert agreement at Level 2 indicates that annotation is consistent across experts. This consistency supports the reliability of the consensus reference label (Ref_N2) and the use of Insta360 as a reference-data source in this type of study.

Compared with conventional field survey, Insta360 provides a permanently stored image record, a standardized perspective, and low additional time requirements for analyzing already available data. Field survey remains necessary for applications that require physical contact, sampling, or laboratory analyses. In the context of visual land-cover classification, however, Insta360 can substantially reduce the need for fieldwork, especially when an archive of previously captured panoramas is available.

5 Conclusions

This study proposes a methodology for the comparative evaluation of Insta360 panoramas against traditional ground-truth data sources for land-cover classification on

the same sample of 50 locations. The results support H1 and H2. Insta360 shows higher informativeness for fine land-cover classes associated with vertical structure, while top-down sources show different levels of agreement with the operational reference standard at the main-class level. The findings suggest that Insta360 can represent a practical compromise between informativeness, reliability, and additional time required to analyze already acquired imagery. The proposed methodology is feasible and adaptable to other areas and land-cover types.

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